

NITROGEN FERTILIZER TYPE AND RATE EFFECTS ON GROWTH AND YIELD RESPONSE OF SOYBEAN VARIETIES

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ABSTRACT

This research was carried to determine the effect of different types and rates of nitrogen (N) fertilizer on growth and yield response of soybean varieties under Umudike ecological conditions, Abia State, Nigeria. Pot experiment was conducted in 2008 outside the green house of Michael Okpara University of Agriculture, Umudike. The response of two varieties of soybean (Tropical Glycine Max-TGX 1440 and TGX 1740) to three different nitrogen fertilizer types (NPK_{15 15 15}, NPK_{20 10 10} and Urea) at four different rates (0, 30, 60 and 90kgN/ha⁻¹) were evaluated. Plant height, number of leaves, stem girth, number of branches per plant, pod number per plant, pod length, number of seed per plant, dry matter weight, dry pod weight and dry seed weight were determined in this work. It was observed that plant height, number of branches, number of seed, dry matter weight and dry pod weight differed significantly at (P < 0.05) in both varieties using different fertilizer types and at different fertilizer rates. TGX 1440 using NPK_{15 15 15} at the rate of 60kg N/ha⁻¹ gave the highest plant height than using NPK_{20 10 10} and Urea and at other rates (0,30 and 90kg N/ha⁻¹) in the same variety and in TGX 1740. Also increased application of nitrogen fertilizer rate increased plant height, dry matter weight, dry pod weight and pod length as in TGX 1440 using NPK_{15 15 15} and NPK_{20 10 10} but decreased pod number per plant and number of seed per plant. From the results TGX 1440 performed using NPK_{15 15 15} at the rate of 60kg N/ha⁻¹. It can therefore be recommended for optimum soybean production in Abia State, Nigeria.

KEYWORDS: soybean, nitrogen fertilizer, growth, yield

INTRODUCTION

Soybean (*Glycine Max* (L) Merrill) is an economically important leguminous crop on a world wide scale and also the most important legume in China (Gan *et al.*, 2003). Soybean is a legume that occupies greater position in world agriculture by virtue of their high protein content and their capacity for fixing atmospheric nitrogen (Osodeke, 2001).

Soybean, unlike most oil seed is a dual purpose plant; the bean of the high yielding variety contains about 18% oil and 38% protein and the extraction residue represents more than 40% of the utilization value of the plant (Ramamani *et al.*, 1996; Mount *et al.*, 1987; Mehmet, 2008).

Soybeans can be used in multiple ways, unprocessed and processed. Soybeans can be processed through roasting, fermentation and germination. Unprocessed de-hulled soybeans have an undesirable flavour and bitterness. Moreover, they contain toxic proteins, haemagglutinins and anti-trypsin (Martin *et al.*, 2010). These substances must be destroyed or deactivated to make the beans palatable and digestible both for human and animal consumption. Soybean is used for soymilk, soy sauce, tofu (soybean curd), yoghurt, flour and in some beverages (FAO, 1992). Soybean grows best in a loose well-drained loam soils, but does tolerate a wide range of soil conditions (Duke, 1983).

The Food and Agriculture Organization of the United Nations (FAO) lists 82 countries that produce soybeans. In 2000 there were 74.1 million hectares of soybean production globally. The United States led all producers with more than 29.3 million hectares. Brazil was second with nearly 13.6 million hectares in production. China was third with more than 9.3 million hectares, Argentina was fourth with 8.6 million hectares, and India was fifth with nearly 6.2 million hectares planted to soybeans. These five countries accounted for 90 percent of land planted to soybeans globally and 92.1 percent of total production (FAO 2002).

The crop was introduced into Nigeria in 1908 (Fernel, 1966). In Nigeria, most soybean production occurs in the middle belt zone consisting of Benue State and other adjoining states where small-scale farmers have been growing soybean for about 50 years (Odeleye *et al.*, 2007). The total annual production of soybean was estimated at 185, 000 tons from 650,000 hectares in Nigeria (FAO, 1996).

Soybean nitrogen requirements are met in a complex manner, as this crop is capable of utilizing both soil nitrogen and atmospheric nitrogen (through symbiotic nitrogen fixation) (Harper, 1974; Milic *et al.*, 2002). The relative nitrogen supply from these two sources can change widely depending on soil nitrogen supply and conditions for nodule development (Varco, 1999; Gan *et al.*, 2003). Nitrogen is one of the most important nutrient elements affecting the yield of soybean (Penal and Wiese, 1987). Over the years, there has been interest in using nitrogen fertilization as a means to increase soybean yield due to the recognition of the large requirement by soybean for high productivity (Yoshihiko and Takaji, 1999). There is not enough information on the fertilizer requirements of soybean from some studies in humid tropical conditions of southern Nigeria (Osodeke 2001).

Despite several years of soybean research in Nigeria, there remains a dearth of empirical information on the optimum levels of nitrogen fertilizer to increase growth and yield of soybean. The aim of this work is to study the effect of different types and rates of nitrogen fertilizer and their interaction on growth and yield response of soybean varieties.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

The study area, Michael Okpara University of Agriculture, Umudike is located approximately at latitude $05^{\circ} 29'N$, longitude $07^{\circ} 32' E$ and altitude 122m above sea level. With a sandy clay loam soil having 0.07% nitrogen content, 4.50 cmolkg^{-1} , phosphorus, 0.06 cmolkg^{-1} , potassium and 2.38% organic matter.

Pot experiments were arranged in a completely randomized design (CRD) in factorial layout with three replications. Soil was collected from 0-15cm depth from portion of land left fallow for 2-3 years. Soil samples were dried, sieved to pass through a 2cm mesh. 10kg of the soil was measured with a weighing balance and filled into each of the 72 pots. Thirty-six pots were set up for each of the two varieties. Each pot was well watered a day before planting.

Seeds were sowed by hand at a seed rate of 3 seeds per pot at 2-3cm depth and 2cm space in between seeds. Seeds germinated 3-4 days after sowing. Thinning was done 2 weeks after sowing (WAS). Fertilizer was applied 2WAS by band method at the control (0 kg N/ha^{-1}), 30, 60 and 90 kg N/ha^{-1} . First weeding was done by hand picking 2WAS and subsequent weeding was done at 2 weeks interval till harvesting.

Data were collected on growth and yield parameters of soybean which include; plant height, stem girth, and pod length all measured in (cm); number of leaves, number of pod per plant, number of branch per plant, number of seed per plant all determined by counting; dry matter weight and seed dry weight in (g) after oven drying using electronic weighing balance with sensitivity of 0.00g.

Plants were harvested 3 months after sowing. Soil was loosened, making it easy to uproot completely without damaging the roots. Data collected were subjected to analysis of variance (ANOVA) using SPSS (2004) computer application package. Significant means were separated using the least significance difference at 5% level of probability.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Soil is sandy clay loam. Sandy loam soil swam up faster, allowing soybean to emerge sooner and develop rapidly. The pH value of the soil in soil water suspension is 4.08 indicating highly acidic nature of the soil. Scharf and Wiebold (2003) noted that soil pH below 6.0 had an average yield of soybean. Huxley (1992) noted that soybean prefers slightly acidic soil. The nutrient concentration (available phosphorus, calcium, magnesium, potassium and sodium) and percentage organic matter content of the soil was very low (Table 1). This shows the need for fertilizer application in this soil for maximum crop performance.

Table 1: Chemical and Physical Properties of Cultivated Soil

Properties	Values
Ph	4.08
% sand	57.10
%silt	19.70
% clay	23.20
Textural Class	Sandy Clay Loam (SCL)
Phosphorus (P)	4.50 cmol Kg ⁻¹
Calcium (Ca)	1.40 cmol Kg ⁻¹
Magnesium (Mg)	1.20 cmol Kg ⁻¹
Potassium (K)	0.06 cmol Kg ⁻¹
Sodium (Na)	0.14 cmol Kg ⁻¹
Total Exchangeable Bases (TEB)	0.14 cmol Kg ⁻¹
% organic Cation	1.38
% Organic matter	2.38
% Nitrogen	0.07

The data pertaining to different agronomic traits on growth and yield parameters of soy bean; at 3-7WAS, maturity and harvest at 10 and 12WAS respectively are presented in Table 2 and 3. Soybean variety, nitrogen N-fertilizer type and rate and their interaction affected agronomic traits in soybean. Table 2 shows the interaction of variety, fertilizer type and fertilizer rate on growth parameters of soybean. However, at week 5, significant difference was observed in the plant height measured using three N fertilizer at control rate (0kg N/ha⁻¹), 30, 60 and 90k N/ha⁻¹ in both varieties.

Variety TGX 1440 using NPK_{15 15 15} at the rate of 60kgNha⁻¹ gave the highest mean value (25.83cm) for plant height at 5WAS compare to other fertilizer types and fertilizer rates in the same variety and in TGX 1740. This finding is in line with Nastasija *et al.*, (2008) who stated that the greatest length, mass and N content of the above ground plant parts were found when 60kg N/ha⁻¹ was applied. Urea gave the least plant height in the two varieties at the rate of 90kg N/ha⁻¹ (in TGX 1440, 13.27cm; TGX 1740, 15.00cm), at week 5 where significant difference was observed.

Plant height increased with increase in N fertilizer rates. Osodeke (2001) reported that increased application of NPK gradually increased plant height and number of leaves per plant. Veron *et al.* (1984) reported an increase in plant height with the application of nitrogen fertilizer. Mehmet (2008) observed that as nitrogen fertilizer rate increased, plant height increased and who also acknowledged Varon *et al.* (1984), Manral and Saxena (2003) and Starling *et al.* (1984) that reported similar result.

Table 3 showed the interaction of variety, fertilizer type and fertilizer rate on yield parameters of soybean at maturity and harvest (10 and 12 WAS). The dry matter weight (DMW), dry pod weight (DPW), number of seed per plant, and number of branches differed significantly at (P < 0.05) in both varieties using different fertilizer types and at different rates.

Table 2: Effects of interaction of variety, fertilizer type and fertilizer rate (kg N/ha⁻¹) on growth parameters of soybean at 3, 5 and 7WAS.

Variety	Fertilizer Type	Fertilizer Rate (kgN/ha)	Plant height (cm)			Number of leaves			Stem girth (cm)		
			WAS			WAS			WAS		
			3	5	7	3	5	7	3	5	7
TGX 1440	NPK 15 15 15	0	11.67 ±3.06	18.67 ^{bcd} ±1.53	27.67 ±5.67	4.33 ±1.15	10.00 ±2.65	18.67 ±7.02	0.20 ±0.10	0.20 ^a ±0.10	0.20 ±0.10
		30	13.83 ±1.76	22.17 ^{ab} ±0.77	30.67 ±3.22	5.00 ±0.00	13.67 ±2.89	20.67 ±4.04	0.17 ±0.06	0.17 ^{ab} ±0.06	0.20 ±0.00
		60	12.67 ±1.15	25.83 ^a ±0.76	34.00 ±3.61	5.33 ±0.58	9.67 ±4.04	20.33 ±3.21	0.20 ±0.00	0.20 ^a ±0.00	0.27 ±0.06
	NPK 20 10 10	0	14.00 ±0.00	14.70 ^c ±3.56	19.57 ±5.44	5.33 ±0.58	7.67 ±1.53	9.67 ±5.03	0.23 ±0.23	0.08 ^b ±0.03	0.08 ±0.03
		30	10.33 ±2.52	21.90 ^{ab} ±1.82	30.33 ±3.21	4.67 ±1.53	9.00 ±1.00	19.67 ±3.79	0.20 ±0.00	0.20 ^a ±0.00	0.20 ±0.05
		60	11.67 ±1.15	22.67 ^{ab} ±1.53	30.67 ±2.52	4.67 ±0.58	10.00 ±1.00	17.00 ±1.00	0.22 ±0.03	0.20 ^a ±0.00	0.23 ±0.06
	Urea	0	10.00 ±2.65	17.67 ^{bcd} ±0.61	25.17 ±2.47	5.00 ±1.00	8.00 ±1.00	10.33 ±1.53	0.13 ±0.06	0.13 ^{ab} ±0.06	0.12 ±0.03
		30	12.00 ±1.73	19.83 ^{bcd} ±1.26	22.33 ±7.22	5.33 ±0.58	6.33 ±2.08	9.33 ±4.73	0.13 ±0.06	0.13 ^{ab} ±0.06	0.12 ±0.03
		60	13.33 ±9.45	16.00 ^{bcd} ±3.04	23.00 ±3.77	5.00 ±2.65	6.67 ±1.53	12.00 ±1.00	0.10 ±0.00	0.10 ^{ab} ±0.00	0.20 ±0.10
	NPK 15 15 15	0	13.33 ±3.21	17.63 ^{bcd} ±3.19	24.10 ±1.65	6.00 ±1.00	5.67 ±0.58	9.33 ±0.58	0.10 ±0.00	0.10 ^{ab} ±0.00	0.23 ±0.06
		30	14.33 ±0.58	19.83 ^{bcd} ±3.01	25.83 4.36	6.00 ±1.00	9.33 ±2.31	8.33 ±4.16	0.17 ±0.06	0.17 ^{ab} ±0.06	0.37 ±0.08
		60	15.83 ±0.76	17.50 ^{cd} ±1.73	24.80 5.03	7.00 ±0.00	8.00 ±0.00	16.67 ±5.13	0.13 ±0.06	0.13 ^{ab} ±0.06	0.35 ±0.00

TGX 1740	90		15.88	19.77 ^{bcd}	26.67	6.00	8.33	15.33	0.20	0.20 ^{ab}	0.33	
			±1.44	±1.27	±4.93	±0.00	±0.58	±1.15	±0.00	±0.00	±0.03	
	NPK 20 10 10	0		11.50	19.50 ^{bcd}	26.67	6.00	8.33	14.33	0.20	0.20 ^{ab}	0.35
				±1.80	±0.50	2.31	±1.00	±1.15	±1.53	±0.00	±0.00	±0.05
		30		13.33	14.63 ^e	20.00	6.00	8.67	14.67	0.10	0.10 ^{ab}	0.37
				±0.58	±2.32	1.50	±1.00	±1.53	±0.58	±0.00	±0.00	±0.03
	Urea	60		14.67	15.50 ^{de}	20.93	7.00	7.00	15.00	0.10	0.10 ^{ab}	0.37
				±1.15	±2.55	9.66	±0.00	±0.00	±5.57	±0.00	±0.00	±0.06
		90		13.00	15.10 ^{ef}	24.33	6.00	7.00	19.33	0.17	0.17 ^{ab}	0.40
				±1.00	±3.87	3.06	±0.00	±1.00	±7.09	±0.06	±0.06	±0.00
	Urea	0		12.67	15.00 ^{ef}	23.00	5.67	7.00	14.00	0.13	0.13 ^{ab}	0.28
				±0.58	±1.73	2.65	±0.58	±1.00	±2.65	±0.06	±0.06	±0.03
		30		12.67	16.33 ^{bcd}	23.83	5.67	8.00	16.00	0.10	0.10 ^{ab}	0.33
				±2.08	±4.04	4.80	±0.58	±1.00	±2.65	±0.00	±0.00	±0.12
Urea	60		11.67	16.00 ^{bcd}	21.67	5.67	6.33	12.33	0.13	0.13 ^{ab}	0.23	
			±2.08	±6.25	2.87	±0.58	±3.28	±7.65	±0.06	±0.06	±0.12	
	90		10.33	15.00 ^{ef}	23.33	4.67	6.33	13.00	0.10	0.10 ^{ab}	0.30	
			±0.58	±2.00	4.93	±0.58	±0.58	±3.00	±0.00	±0.00	±0.10	

Table 3: Effects of interaction of variety, fertilizer type and fertilizer rate on yield parameters of soybean measured at maturity (10 WAS) and at harvest (12WAS)

Variety	Fertilizer Type	Fertilizer Rate	Parameter at harvest								
			Plant girth	No of branches	No of pod	No of Seed	Pod Length	Dry matter weight	Dry Pod weight	Dry Seed Weight	
TGX 1440	NPK 15 15 15	0	0.28	6.67 ^{ab}	29.00a	51.33 ^a	4.02	7.84 ^{ab}	5.24 ^{ab}	3.54	
			±0.13	±2.31	±11.53	±25.70	±0.69	±6.86	±2.98	±2.04	
	Urea	30	0.27	5.33 ^{bcd}	22.33 ^{abc}	37.33 ^{ab}	3.73	6.19 ^{abcd}	5.24 ^{ab}	3.75	
			±0.12	±1.15	±5.13	±6.11	±0.46	±2.31	±0.60	±0.35	
		60	0.40	5.00 ^{bcd}	16.33 ^{abc}	32.67 ^{bc}	4.07	6.48 ^{abc}	3.26 ^{bcd}	2.27	
			±0.00	±2.00	±10.97	±23.67	±0.15	±2.36	±1.56	±1.22	
	Urea	90	0.40	5.00 ^{bcd}	21.67 ^{abc}	40.00 ^{ab}	4.30	9.26 ^a	9.11 ^a	3.42	
			±0.10	±1.73	±14.36	±26.66	±0.10	±1.86	±8.28	±0.93	
		NPK 20 10 10	0	0.17	2.00 ^{ef}	5.33 ^{ijk}	9.33 ^{ef}	3.73	1.92 ^{ij}	1.14 ^{cd}	0.76
			±0.12	±0.00	±2.08	±3.06	±0.60	±1.00	±0.74	±0.57	
Urea	30	0.37	8.00 ^a	22.33 ^{abc}	41.00 ^{ab}	4.47	8.61 ^{ab}	5.25 ^{ab}	3.46		

			±0.06	±1.73	±4.73	±9.17	±1.12	±2.46	±1.32	±1.19
		60	0.40	6.00 ^{ab}	22.67 ^{ab}	37.00 ^{ab}	4.37	9.19 ^{ab}	5.08 ^{bc}	3.43
			±0.10	±1.00	±3.21	±15.72	±0.32	±1.55	±1.34	±1.10
		90	0.37	3.33 ^{cd}	13.00 ^{efc}	13.00 ^{def}	4.00	4.36 ^{fg}	2.58 ^{bcd}	1.25
			±0.06	±0.58	±4.36	±4.36	±0.36	±0.17	±0.20	±0.74
	Urea	0	0.20	3.33 ^{cd}	3.33 ^k	6.67 ^l	3.40	1.92 ^{ij}	0.83 ^{cd}	0.53
			±0.17	±0.58	±0.58	±1.15	±0.17	±0.37	±0.29	±0.23
		30	0.23	1.33 ^{ef}	3.67 ^{jk}	7.00 ^{ef}	3.40	1.24 ^{ijk}	0.58 ^d	0.38
			±0.06	±1.15	±0.58	±1.73	±0.61	±0.81	±0.96	±0.19
		60	0.33	0.67 ^f	4.33 ^{jk}	7.67 ^{ef}	3.20	1.86	0.69 ^d	0.38
			±0.25	±0.58	±1.53	±1.53	±0.20	±0.66	±0.29	±0.20
		90	0.20	1.33 ^{ef}	6.33	11.00 ^{def}	3.33	1.78 ^{ij}	1.03 ^{cd}	0.68
			±0.00	±1.15	±4.51	±8.54	±0.29	±1.02	±0.61	±0.42
TGX	NPK	0	0.25	5.00 ^{bcd}	22.33 ^{abc}	27.00 ^{bcd}	4.30	3.89 ^{ij}	3.25 ^{bcd}	3.67
1740	15 15 15		±0.13	±3.61	±4.29	±4.00	±0.52	±4.56	±2.36	±4.51
		30	0.22	4.67 ^{bcd}	19.33 ^{abcd}	35.33 ^{ab}	4.60	5.35 ^{abcdef}	2.51 ^{bcd}	1.60
			±0.10	±0.58	±9.50	±8.33	±0.53	±3.69	±0.96	±0.66
		60	0.33	5.33 ^{bcd}	12.67 ^{efc}	23.00 ^{bcd}	4.30	5.84 ^{abcde}	3.76 ^{bcd}	2.86
			±0.15	±0.58	±5.86	±11.14	±1.15	±3.52	±0.95	±0.10
		90	0.23	5.67 ^{abc}	11.67 ^{fg}	23.33 ^{bcd}	4.23	5.13 ^{abcdef}	2.52 ^{bcd}	1.94
			±0.06	±2.31	±2.52	±4.23	±0.49	±3.48	±1.16	±1.23
	NPK	0	0.32	3.33 ^{cd}	5.67 ^{ij}	9.67 ^{ef}	3.63	7.26 ^{abc}	1.30 ^{cd}	0.75
	20 10 10		±0.08	±1.15	±1.52	±2.52	±0.71	±4.83	±0.74	±0.34
		30	0.23	3.00 ^{df}	6.67 ⁱ	18.33 ^{cdef}	3.97	6.00 ^{abcde}	1.39 ^{cd}	0.33
			±0.12	±1.00	±3.21	±0.58	±1.45	±1.88	±1.15	±0.37
		60	0.30	3.33 ^{cd}	8.00 ^{fgh}	15.00 ^{cdef}	3.60	5.61 ^{abcdef}	1.19 ^{cd}	0.67
			±0.00	±0.58	±4.00	±7.21	±0.40	±2.21	±0.93	±0.41
		90	0.43	5.67 ^{abc}	16.00 ^{abcd}	29.67 ^{bcd}	3.63	5.02 ^{abcdef}	3.25 ^{bcd}	1.56
			±0.21	±0.58	±2.65	±4.93	±0.45	±1.61	±1.46	±0.53
	Urea	0	0.40	3.00 ^{df}	5.00 ^{ijk}	10.33 ^{ef}	3.00	2.96 ^{fjh}	0.91 ^{cd}	0.43
			±0.10	±1.00	±1.73	±1.53	±0.50	±1.09	±0.41	±0.32
		30	0.30	2.00 ^{ef}	8.33 ^{gh}	15.00 ^{cdef}	2.30	4.19 ^{fg}	1.65 ^{bcd}	0.93
			±0.17	±0.00	±3.21	±8.66	±0.72	±3.36	±0.89	±0.53
		60	0.43	3.00 ^{df}	14.33 ^{ef}	27.00 ^{bcd}	3.53	3.81 ^{fg}	4.32 ^{bc}	2.60
			±0.12	±3.00	±2.08	±6.08	±0.64	±1.53	±2.93	±1.92
		90	0.27	3.33 ^{cd}	13.67 ^{ef}	25.33 ^{bcd}	3.27	4.84 ^{bcd}	2.46 ^{bcd}	1.27
			±0.12	±2.52	±6.81	±13.32	±0.64	±13.32	±2.40	±1.41

TGX 1440 using NPK_{15 15 15} gave the highest mean values for number of seed per plant and pod number at the rate 0kg N/ha⁻¹. This observation in line with Nastasija *et al.*, (2008) that the greatest number of seeds and number of pods were obtained at the rate of 0kg N/ha⁻¹.

The number of branches obtained from using NPK_{15 15 15} from rate 0kg N/ha⁻¹ – 90kg N/ha⁻¹ in both varieties were consistent and so remained unchanged. This report agreed with Chiezey and Yayok (1991) who observed that number of branches of soybean remained unchanged with increase in nitrogen levels. However, Christmas (2002) reported increase in number of branches with increase in the nitrogen doses.

Also observed was the highest mean values for dry matter weight and dry pod weight in TGX 1440 using NPK_{15 15 15} at the rate of 90kg/ha⁻¹. George and Singleton (1982) reported that the dry matter mass of total number of soybean grown in two locations increased significantly when increase amount of mineral N was incorporated into the soil.

Generally, it was observed that most fertilizer types performed better at other rates than the control (0kg N/ha⁻¹) in most parameters of soybean researched. This work therefore revealed the need for fertilizer application to increase soybean yield for higher performance. Yoshihiko (1991) recognized the use and need of nitrogen fertilizer as a means of increasing soybean yield for high productivity.

CONCLUSION

The research revealed that the application of nitrogen fertilizer is very important as a means of increasing yield in soybean. Both varieties of soybean used in this research responded differently to different types and rates of nitrogen fertilizers on most growth and yield parameters measured. However, TGX 1440 using NPK_{15 15 15} performed best and at the rate of 60kg N/ha⁻¹ than using other fertilizer types and at other rates in the same variety and in TGX 1740 on most growth and yield parameters researched. It can be concluded from the results that TGX 1440 using NPK_{15 15 15} at the rate of 60kg N/ha⁻¹ can be recommended for optimum soybean production in Abia State, Nigeria.

REFERENCES

- Chiezey, U.F. and Yayok, J.Y. (1999). Performance of soybean as affected by variety, nitrogen and potassium fertilizer levels. *Nigerian Agricultural Journal*. 26:45 – 58.
- Christmas, E.P. (2002). Plant Populations and Seedling Rates for Soybean: Purdue University Cooperative Extension Service. West Lafayette, India.
- Duke, J.A. (1983). *Excellent Information on a wide range of plants*. Handbook of Energy Crop. www.notulaeobotanicae.org.USA
- F.A.O. (1996). Production Year Book, Vol. 50. Food and Agricultural Organization, Rome.
- F.A.O. (2002). FAOSTAT statistics database. UN Food and Agriculture Organization, Rome. <http://apps.fao.org>.
- F.A.O. (1992). Technology of production of edible flours and protein products from soybeans. FAO, Agricultural Services *Bulletin* No. 97.
- Fernel, M.A. (1966). Present status of research on edible legumes in Western Nigeria. Paper presented at the First Nigerian Legume Conference, IITA, Ibadan, Nigeria.
- Gan, Y; Stulen, I; Posrhuimus, F; Keulen, H and Peter, J.C. (2002). Effects of N management on growth, N₂ fixation and yield of soybean. *Nutrient cycling Agroecosyst*. 62:163 – 174.
- George, T.P. and Singleton, W. (1992). Nitrogen assimilation traits and dinitrogen fixation in soybean and common bean. *Agronomy Journal*. 84: 1020 – 1028.
- Harper, J.E. (1974). Soil and symbiotic requirements for optimum soybean production. *Crop Science*. 14:255 – 260.

- Huxley A. (1992). The New RHS Dictionary of Gardening. Macmillan Press, London.
- Manral, H.S. and Saxena, S.C. (2003). Plant growth, yield attributes and grain yield of soybean as affected by the sources of nutrients. *Bioresources and Technological Journal*. 92:110-118.
- Martin H, Laswai H, and Kulwa K. (2010). Nutrient content and acceptability of soybean based complementary food. *African Journal of Food, Agriculture, Nutrition and Development*. 10(1):2040-2049.
- Mehmet, O.Z. (2008). Nitrogen rate and plant population effects of yield components in soybean. *African Journal Biotechnology*. 7(24): 4464 – 4470.
- Milic, V., Nastagsija, M and Milica, H. (2003). Interrelationship of nitrogen fixation potential and soybean yield. *A Periodical of Scientific Research on Field and Vegetable Crops*. 36; 133 – 139.
- Mounts, T.L., Wolf, W.J. Martinez W.H. (1987). Processing and utilization. In: Soybean's improvement, production and uses, (Second edition), J.R. Wilcox, Madison, Wisconsin.
- Nastajja, M; Jelena, M. and Acimelic, R. (2008). Effect of N fertilizer application on growth and yield of inoculated soybean. *Notulae Botanicae Horticultural Cluj – Napoca* 36 (1): 48 – 57.
- Odeleye, F.O., Odeleye, O.M.O and Animashaun, M.O. (2007). Effects of Nutrient Foliar Spray on Soybean Growth and Yield. *Glycine Max (L) Merrill*. *Not. Bot. Hort. Agrobot. Cluj*. 35(2): 22-32.
- Osodeke, U.E. (2001). Yield performance, N₂ – fixation and Fertilizer Requirement of Soybean [(*Glycine Max(L) Merrill*)] in some Soils of the Forest Zone of South eastern Nigeria. Ph.D Dissertation. Department of Soil Science and Agro-climatology, Micheal Okpara University of Agriculture, Umudike, Nigeria.
- Penas, E.J., Wiese R.A. (1987). Fertilizer suggestions for soybeans. Neb guide 987-859 A, University of Nebraska, Cooperative Extension, Lincoln, NE.
- Ramamani S., Chandrasekhara H.N. and Narasimba, M.K. (1996). Efficiency of inactivation of trypsin and haemagglutinins by roasting of soybean (*Glycine max*). *Journal of Food Science and Technology*. 33: 197-201.
- Scharf P.C and Wiebold, W.J. (2003). Soybean yield responds minimally to nitrogen applications in Missouri. *Plant Management Network*. 10: 1094-1117.
- Starling, M.E., Wood C.W., and Weaver, D.B. (1998). Starter nitrogen and growth habit effects on late – planted soybean. *Agronomy Journal*. 90: 658 – 662.
- Varco, J.J. (1999). Nitrogen and Fertility Requirements. In: Soybean Production in Midsouth. Hearthlerly L.G. and Hodges H.F. (Eds). CRC Press, Boca Raton, F.L.
- Varon, R.C.A, Munoz, B.D, Covalada, Z.F, and Medina, U.O. (1984). Effect of level and stage of N fertilizer application and *Rhizobium* inoculation on soybean field in Ibague. *Revista Institute Columbia Agropecuario.*, 19(3): 291-295.
- Yoshihiko, T. and Takuji, O. (1999). *Technique for Deep Placement of Coated Urea Fertilizer in Soybean Cultivation*. Nigata Agricultural Research Institute, Crop Research Centre, Nigata University, Japan.

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